

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10845728>

ISSUES OF DIGITALIZATION OF MEDICINE IN UZBEKISTAN

Siddiqova Sadokat Ghaforovna

Rector of the Bukhara Engineering Technological Institute,

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences,

sadoqats@mail.ru

Saidjonova Parvina Shukhratovna

manager of "City Sport Bukhara" LLC, freelance researcher

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada tibbiyot tizimini raqamlashtirish, teletibbiyot tibbiy xizmatlarni zamonaviy texnik va telekommunikatsiya vositalari orqali takomillashtirish, tibbiyot muassasalarining axborot ta'minotini yaxshilash imkoniyatlari, tibbiyot sohasini raqmalashtirishning tibbiy soha faoliyatini osonlashtirish, aniqlashtirish va ixchamlashtirish shart-sharoitlari haqida firkmulohazalar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *tibbiyot, raqamlashtirish, tibbiy soha, teletibbiyot, axborot ta'minoti, raqamli tibbiyot, mijoz, imkoniyat*

Abstract. In this article, opinions are expressed about the digitalization of the medical system, the improvement of telemedicine medical services through modern technical and telecommunication tools, the possibilities of improving the information supply of medical institutions, the conditions for the digitization of the medical field, the conditions for facilitating, clarifying and compacting the activities of the medical field.

Keywords: medicine, digitization, medical field, telemedicine, information supply, digital medicine, customer, opportunity.

The New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan was created by the Decree No. PF-60 of 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This development strategy consists of seven priorities, in which the main issue is building a just society and glorifying human dignity as an urgent issue.

Digitization issues are one of the main sections of the strategy. Digitization and innovation sector in Uzbekistan has its own problems and directions of application and growth. This is mainly to increase the infrastructure, technologies, information technologies, electronics, telecommunications, multinational enterprises, start-ups, branches, incubators and cooperation establishment bodies and other entities, to provide a social, economic, architectural and consensus environment for socio-economic implementation. fully covers.

Also, on December 28, 2023, the Decision PQ-415 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the acceleration of digitization of the healthcare system and additional measures to introduce advanced digital technologies" was adopted. The widespread use of digital technologies is one of the main factors in the rapid development of the health care system, which is gaining popularity in many countries. Thanks to telemedicine, people's time and material resources are saved.

He will be able to choose a clinic and a doctor sitting at home. At the same time, he uses medical services equally and easily. In other words, telemedicine is receiving medical services at a distance through modern technical and telecommunication means. Online telediagnosis allows our compatriots to receive advice from the most advanced local and foreign experts without leaving their homes. As a result, patients save time and money, get rid of travel and other difficulties.

Relationships in any field, including telemedicine, need legal regulation. Medical law is a rapidly developing branch of current jurisprudence, which involves the legal regulation of all health care relations. In this sense, telemedicine is a

regulatory subject of medical law. By now, many countries have passed telemedicine laws. In our country, the adoption of a special law regulating telemedicine is reflected in the state program.

Here, the law on telemedicine serves to legally regulate the complex processes of telemedicine for our country. Ensures priority of law. Defines the rights and obligations of all participants in the telemedicine process.

Digitization of the medical system opens up a wide area and opportunity to solve a number of problems typical not only for our country, but for any country, especially the lack of quality medicine in rural areas. In this regard, countries such as USA, Japan, Great Britain, Germany, Australia, Greece, Ireland, Spain, Canada, France, Sweden, Switzerland are very advanced. Also, many telemedicine projects are being implemented effectively in Russia, Ukraine, Belarus, Moldova, Georgia, Armenia, and Kazakhstan.

Digitalization of medicine is the process of introducing and using IT technologies and digital services in the industry, which affects all processes - from managing the healthcare system to the practical activities of doctors in the field.

The medical industry regularly faces various challenges related to the optimization of standard processes.

Representatives of the healthcare system note positive changes in these areas as a result of the introduction of advanced technologies. Examples of digitalization include telemedicine consultations, online patient registration, automation of accounting systems, electronic document management, Internet of Medical Things.

Digitalization will also introduce new tasks, such as the introduction of new technologies in medicine under the guise of roadmap information systems. The launch of a new subsystem called Occupational Pathology was announced, in addition to the already existing ones in cardiology, oncology, and non-anotology.

Figure 1. The main features of the software

The main features of the software for medical institutions:

- ✚ built-in registry;
- ✚ patient records are maintained;
- ✚ medical CRM system;
- ✚ marketing;
- ✚ telephony and call center;
- ✚ medical records;
- ✚ inventory control.

Even before the start of the pandemic, the task was set to relieve the call processing department staff. And this problem arose in all industries that switched to remote work. Failures were observed even before the peak number of requests. It was possible to significantly reduce the load on operators with the help of so-called smart assistants. Voice assistants processed more than 50% of calls to hotlines. To implement the system, additional computing resources were required. In conditions of restrictions, they could be obtained through cloud solutions. External resources reduced the amount of time required to launch the service. The costs of storing large volumes of information were significantly reduced.

This means that digitalization in medicine and healthcare makes medical services more familiar, and it is more convenient to receive them through services. Many experts have already verified the effectiveness of delegating health management to services. There is also the prospect of a subscription model, with which you can get expert advice and create a health management plan. Access to medical services is provided on an ongoing basis.

REFERENCES

1. Сиддикова, С. Г., & Юлдашев, Ш. С. (2014). Создание и использование электронных учебников. *ИННОВАЦИИ, КАЧЕСТВО И СЕРВИС В ТЕХНИКЕ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯХ* (pp. 303-304).
2. Сиддикова, С. Г. (2015). АВТОМАТИЗАЦИЯ СИСТЕМ ЗАЩИТЫ ИНФОРМАЦИИ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ МЕТОДОВ ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ. In *Современные инструментальные системы, информационные технологии и инновации* (pp. 73-77).
3. Zebo, T. X., & E'zoza, E. (2023). OLIY TA'LIMDA TALABALAR BILAN OLIV BORILADIGAN O 'QUV-METODIK VA MA'NAVIY-MA'RIFIY ISHLARNING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(17), 489-496.
4. Sharifovna, T. Z., & Bakhriniso, T. (2020). Modernization of higher education by solving integration problems. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(12 Part II), 44-49.
5. Sh, T. Z., & Kh, S. K. (2020). Innovative forms of education in Uzbekistan. *International journal of innovations in engineering research and technology. IJIERT*, 7(4), 258-261.
6. Тухтаева, З. Ш., & Искандарова, Г. Б. (2014). Пути осуществления межпредметной связи и преемственности. *Молодой ученый*, (8), 884-887.
7. Тухтаева, З. Ш. (2018). Олий таълимда ихтисослик ва мутахассислик фанлар узвийлиги ва интеграциясини таъминлаш муаммолари. *Касб-хунар таълим*, (4), 21.